

The Action of Carbon Tetrachloride on Certain Mercaptans.

BY SRI KRISHNA AND SAJJAN SINGH.

Reimer and Tiemann (*Ber.*, 1876, 9, 1285; 1877, 10, 824) investigated the action of carbon tetrachloride on phenols in alkaline solution, and they found that carbon tetrachloride is but slowly acted upon when heated with an aqueous solution of phenol in excess of alkali, but in alcoholic solution the reaction proceeds more rapidly, the products being *ortho*- and *para*-hydroxybenzoic acids. The products, however, are quite different when the conditions of the experiment are slightly altered, for instance, the production of aurine and rosolic acid from phenol and salicylaldehyde which is an intermediate product, under the dehydrating influence of the excess of alkali (*Ber.* 1877, 10, 824). It, therefore, seems that the action of carbon tetrachloride and chloroform on phenols does not always proceed as has been shown by Reimer and Tiemann. Employing zinc chloride as a condensing agent Sen, Sinha and Sarkar (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 1, 303) have obtained benzeins from phenols and chloroform.

An attempt has now been made to study the products that result from mercaptans when heated with carbon tetrachloride and alkalis according to the above method. As a result of this investigation it is found that unsubstituted thiophenol gives thiosalicylic acid together with a large quantity of its disulphide. Substituted thiophenols, on the other hand, produce an acid from their disulphides.

This shows that the action of alkali firstly is to convert the mercaptan into a disulphide. This, however, is not in accordance with the previous experiments where the disulphide is broken up by the alkalis to form mercaptans (Schiller and Otto, *Ber.*, 1876, 9, 1637; Smiles and Steward, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 119, 1794):

The formation of the thiol derivatives from the disulphide indicates that rupture of the dithio-system has taken place, and since it cannot be supposed that under these conditions the change is due to direct reduction by any reagent present, it must be assumed that the process is primarily one of hydrolysis which is effected by the alkali hydroxide. In the present case, high temperature and pressure at which the experiment is performed are probably responsible for the production of the disulphide.

The view that an acid from the disulphide is one of the products, is found to be correct, as it can be very easily reduced to the corresponding mercaptan and the acid from the mercaptan:

Possibilities of the reaction taking a different course from what is shown above are many, e.g.,

Such is not the case is borne out by the experimental results, unless we assume that on reduction the hydrolysis of the carbonyl group takes place:

The yield of the products obtained is very small and in none of the experiments has it been more than 12 per cent. It makes no difference in the yields of the final products, whether sodium or potassium hydroxide is employed. This is brought out because Reimer and Tiemann (*loc. cit.*) insist on using potassium hydroxide for obtaining good results, especially in presence of small amounts of alcohol. The results obtained in the present work show that the presence of alcohol in howsoever small a quantity is detrimental to the success of the experiment.

Efforts have been made to improve the yield of the products by employing suitable catalysts. Shah (*J. Indian Inst. Sci.*, 1924, 20) has successfully employed reduced copper in similar condensations of aniline and carbon tetrachloride, but in these experiments it is found that reduced copper and reduced nickel inhibit the reaction.

The effect of temperature and the length of heating have also been noticed as shown in the following tables:—

Temperature.	Hrs. of heating.	Percentage of thiol acid.	Other products.
100-110°	24	12	} Small quantity of silica and the rest unchanged together with resinous products.
120-130°	24	4	
130-140°	24	3	} Resinous products.
150-160°	24	nil	

Length of heating at 100-110°.

Hrs. of heating.	Percentage of the acid formed.
6	2
8	4
16	6
24	12
32	8
40	5
48	3

On longer heating various resinous, noncrystallisable products were formed.

The usual method of preparing thiophenol from benzenesulphonic acid and phosphorous pentachloride and the reduction of the resulting sulphonyl chloride is found to be lengthy and tedious; it was, therefore, prepared directly from benzene and chlorosulphonic acid. The details of the method are given below.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Thiophenol, $C_6H_5.SH$.—Into a flask containing chlorosulphonic acid (600 g., 5 mols.) cooled to 0° was added drop by drop from a separating funnel pure dry benzene (80 g.) in the course of an hour. As soon as a drop came in contact with chlorosulphonic acid, hydrogen chloride was evolved and the temperature rose. In order to avoid any undue rise in temperature, the mixture was thoroughly stirred. When whole of the benzene had been added, the mixture was warmed on a water-bath for an hour at $65-70^\circ$. The mixture was cooled and poured over crushed ice, when benzene sulphonyl chloride separated out as a white solid (yield 80 per cent.). The acid water was drained off and more ice added. The process was repeated thrice when most of the acid was got rid off. It is difficult to filter the sulphonyl chloride on a water-pump, as it melts at a low temperature.

The sulphonyl chloride (20 g.) thus obtained was then added in small portions to cooled (0°) 50 per cent. sulphuric acid (80 c.c.) and the calculated quantity of zinc dust (40 g.) was added to the mixture without letting the temperature rise. The flask was then fitted with a reflux condenser and shaken for half an hour, any rise in temperature being avoided. The mixture was then heated on a small flame for five hours and then steam distilled when thiophenol came over as a pale yellow liquid.

o-Thiolbenzoic Acid.—A mixture of potassium hydroxide (36 g.) dissolved in a small quantity of water, thiophenol (12 g.) and carbon tetrachloride (17 g.) were sealed in a thick glass tube and heated in a furnace at $100-110^\circ$ for 24 hours. The contents of the tube (yellow liquid and brownish red solid) were washed into a beaker and excess of carbon tetrachloride removed on a water-bath. On cooling the mixture was extracted with ether to remove unacted thiophenol and disulphide, and the aqueous layer, after filtration, was rendered acidic when a yellow precipitate settled down. It

crystallised from alcohol as white needles, m.p. 177°. The analysis agreed with the formula for *o*-thiolbenzoic acid. (Literature gives the m.p. 165° for *o*-thiolbenzoic acid). The potassium salt was prepared and the analysis again showed this to be that of thiolbenzoic acid.

4:4'-Dichloro-6' (?) -carboxyl diphenyl disulphide (SH:Cl:COOH=1:4:6') was obtained by heating molecular proportions of *p*-chlorothiophenol and carbon tetrachloride in a sealed tube for 24 hours at 110°. The contents of the tube, on removal of CCl₄ and resinous matter, were acidified and the white precipitate thus formed was collected and crystallised; m.p. 210-12°. (Found: S, 19·67; Cl, 21·42. C₁₂H₈O₂Cl₂S₂ requires S, 19·33; Cl, 21·45 per cent).

Thiol-4-chloro-2 (?) -benzoic acid (SH: Cl: COOH=1:4:2) was obtained from the above disulphide on reduction with zinc and hydrochloric acid in alcoholic solution. On pouring the mixture in water an oil and a solid separated. The oil, on keeping, solidified and was identified as *p*-chlorothiophenol, and the solid, on crystallisation from alcohol, gave colourless needles, m.p. 110°. (Found: S, 17·65; Cl, 18·50; C, 44·04; H, 2·83. C₇H₅O₂SCl requires S, 16·97; Cl, 18·83; C, 44·56; H, 2·64 per cent.).

2:2': 5:5' Tetrachloro-6' (?) -carboxyl diphenyl disulphide.— This was prepared from 1:4-dichlorothiophenol and carbon tetrachloride. It crystallised from acetic acid in plates, m.p. 176°. (Found: S, 16·29; Cl, 35·22. C₁₂H₈O₂S₂Cl₄ requires Cl, 35·50; S, 16·00 per cent.).

Thiol-2:5-dichloro-6 (?) -benzoic acid (SH: Cl: Cl: COOH=1:2:5:6) was formed when the above disulphide was carefully reduced in acetic acid solution with zinc dust. On dilution with water, the products were separated on treatment with sodium carbonate. The acid obtained on neutralisation with mineral acids was crystallised from alcohol in needles, m. p. 122° (D.R.P. 294375 gives no melting point.) (Found: C, 37·55; H, 3·10; Cl, 31·44; S, 14·60. C₇H₅O₂Cl₂S requires C, 37·66; H, 1·79; Cl, 31·83; S, 14·35 per cent.).

4:4'-Dimethyl-3' (?) -carboxyl diphenyl disulphide was obtained from *p*-tolyl mercaptan and carbon tetrachloride. It was crystallised from acetic acid in needles, m.p. 156°. (Found: S, 21·71. C₁₄H₁₄O₂S₂ requires S, 22·06 per cent.).

Thiol-4-methyl-3 (?) -benzoic acid (SH:CH₃:COOH=1:4:3) was obtained from the above disulphide on reduction in acetic acid solution. It crystallises in needles, m.p. 82° (D. R. P. 216269

gives no melting point). (Found: C, 56.71; H, 5.01; S, 18.90. $C_8H_8O_2S$ requires C, 57.14; H, 4.76; S, 19.04 per cent.).

4:4'-Diamino-3(?)-carboxyl diphenyl disulphide hydrochloride was prepared from *p*-nitrothiophenol and CCl_4 . It crystallises from alcohol in colourless plates and chars at 280° . (Found: Cl, 19.21; S, 17.73. $C_{12}H_{12}O_2Cl_2N_2S$ requires S, 17.53; Cl, 19.45 per cent.).

Thiol-4-amino-3(?) -benzoic acid hydrochloride (SH:NH₂:COOH = 1:4:3) was prepared from the above disulphide on reduction with zinc and hydrochloric acid. (Found: C, 40.38; H, 4.21; N, 6.60. $C_7H_8O_2NSCl$ requires C, 40.87; H, 3.89; N, 6.81 per cent.).

4:4'-Dibromo-6(?) -carboxyl diphenyl disulphide was prepared from *p*-bromothiophenol and carbon tetrachloride. It crystallises from acetic acid in needles, m. p. $241-42^\circ$. (Found: Br, 37.83; S, 15.69. $C_{12}H_{10}O_2S_2Br_2$ requires Br, 38.09, S, 15.20 per cent.).

On reduction in acetic acid solution with zinc dust it gives *p*-bromothiophenol and *thiol-4-bromo-3(?) -benzoic acid* (SH:Br:COOH = 1:4:3), which crystallises from alcohol in silky needles, m. p. 210° . (Found: C, 35.65; H, 3.11; S, 14.01; Br, 33.93. $C_7H_6O_2SBr$ requires C, 36.05; H, 2.14; S, 13.73; Br, 34.33 per cent.).